

Human-Eval-Java-Infill

This file contains the Human-Eval Java dataset used in this study. The 'src' directory is organized into two subdirectories:

1. Main Subdirectory:

- **Buggy directory:** Contains 163 Java files, each with a single masked line of code, where the masked line represents a bug.
- **Correct directory:** Contains the corrected versions of the buggy files.
- **Answer file:** Provides the correct version of each masked line for the buggy programs. These entries are not listed in sequential order but can easily be located by searching for the class name (e.g., 'ADD_ELEMENTS').

2. Test Subdirectory:

- Contains 163 test suites, with each test suite corresponding to one of the 163 Java files in the Main Subdirectory.

Experiment_Results_Summary

This file contains the results of experiments for all 20 models. Within the folder, a PDF file named `Model_Evaluation_Metrics` provides a detailed description of the metrics used to assess the models' performance in generating correct and diverse solutions. It includes information on model parameters, computational efficiency, output characteristics, and error analysis for both $N = 1$ and $N = 5$. Please refer to the **Model_Evaluation_Metrics** file for a comprehensive explanation of these metrics.

Detailed_Experiment_Outputs

This file contains the comprehensive raw data from running each of the 20 models on all 163 buggy programs. This data includes the results generated by each model before any analysis or summarization. It serves as the foundation for subsequent analysis, which leads to the results summarized in the `Experiment_Results_Summary` directory.

The directory is organized as follows:

- **20 Model sub-directories:** Each subdirectory corresponds to one of the 20 models. Within each model subdirectory, you'll find 28 to 30 additional subdirectories (depending on the model), each representing a different configuration for beam search and nucleus sampling. Each of these subdirectories contains five directories, named **result0** to **result4**, which store the results for five infills across all 163 buggy programs. A summary of the results for these infills is provided in the **results.json** file.

Research_Questions_Data_Analysis.xlsx

This Excel file contains extracted data from the results, organized to address the research questions and support statistical analysis.

The Implemented Tool

The **CLMEvaluationProject.zip** contains all scripts and configuration files necessary for executing the models used in line infilling tasks. It is designed to streamline setup, execution, and configuration. A README file is included with detailed instructions on configuring and running the models.

How to Set Up and Run the Tool

Detailed instructions on configuring, running, and interpreting the output can be found in the README file within the provided ZIP file. Additionally, a comprehensive guide on setting up and using the tool is provided below.

Structure of the Directories

- The **clm** directory contains a Python application that offers mask prediction capabilities for 20 CLMs, using a unified input and output format. It also includes an API for programmatic access.
- The **experiments** directory includes files for evaluating the infill generation abilities of the 20 CLMs (refer to [README.md](experiments/clm-infill-benchmark/README.md)).

Requirements

The experiments were conducted on Windows. Some minor adjustments may be needed to run them on macOS or Linux.

- JDK 17
- Maven
- Python 3.9 or greater
- CUDA (for running CLMs on Nvidia GPUs)

Installation

Dependencies for the **clm** package are managed using **Poetry** and can be installed via either <https://github.com/python-poetry/poetry> or Pip. Navigate to the project directory and choose one of the following options:

```
``shell
# Using Pip
pip install .

# Using Pip (development mode)
pip install -e .

# Using Poetry
poetry install # Install dependencies
poetry shell # Activate virtual environment
````
```

For Windows, make sure the required C++ Build Tools, including **MSVC v143 - VS 2022 C++ x64/x86 Build Tools**, are installed. You can install them via the Visual Studio Installer by selecting the component.

### ### Usage

The CLM package can be used independently for experimenting with mask prediction across various CLMs, either through the command line (CLI) or via the API.

### ### Mask Prediction CLI

The example below demonstrates a basic mask prediction command. First, navigate to the `clm` directory. The input file should include a `<mask>`, which serves as the universal mask token that will be converted to the appropriate format for each CLM.

To view the list of available CLMs and their variants, either enter an invalid CLM name to see the options or check the `MaskPredictModel` subclasses in the `clm/clms` folder. Remember to use lowercase for the model name (e.g., `santacoder` instead of `SantaCoder`).

**Note:** On the first run, the model will be downloaded and stored in a cache directory. On Windows, it is typically saved in

`C:\Users\\.cache\huggingface\hub`. Subsequent runs will load the model from this cached directory.

```
``shell

Usage info
python mask_predict.py --help

Example usages
python mask_predict.py codet5 --model-variant=large ./inputs/abs_expr.py
python mask_predict.py codet5 --model-variant=large ./inputs/abs_expr.py --nr-beams=5
python mask_predict.py codet5 --model-variant=large ./inputs/abs_expr.py --top-p=0.5 temperature=1
python mask_predict.py codet5 --model-variant=large ./inputs/abs_expr.py --quantization-mode=8bit

#For smaller model you can run them on CPU instead of GPU
python mask_predict.py codet5 --model-variant=large ./inputs/abs_expr.py --nr-beams=5 --device="cpu"
python mask_predict.py unixcoder ./inputs/abs_expr.py --nr-beams=5 --device="cpu"
...

```

### ### Mask Prediction API

The Mask Prediction API provides similar functionality to the CLI tool but is designed for use in a web API context. It is particularly useful for integrating mask prediction capabilities into code-based projects.

Although this section is not included in the paper submitted to GPCE 2025, it may be valuable for users looking to combine mask prediction with other techniques, such as search-based methods, in an API-based application.

### Important Notes:

- The API has been tested on Linux systems; minor adjustments may be needed for other operating systems, like Windows.
- You will need to write your own code to interact with the API and perform mask predictions.
- For the experiments in the GPCE 2025 paper, the Mask Prediction CLI is recommended, as discussed earlier.

To start the API, use the following commands:

```
```shell
flask --app clm.api.api run # Standard mode
flask --app clm.api.api --debug run # Debug/development mode
```
```

Flask's development mode enables automatic reloading of the API when code changes.

### ### API Endpoints

Currently, the API provides a single endpoint.

#### ### POST /mask\_predict

- **Path parameters:** None
- **Query parameters:** None
- **Request body:**

```
```json
{
  "text": "def hello_world(): <mask>", // Input with <mask> token
  "model_name": "unixcoder", // Name of the CLM
  "model_variant": null, // CLM variant, available options differ per CLM
  "nr_results": 10 // Number of mask predictions to generate, defaults to 10
}
```
```